

Momentum = E(v)v From Flux/Flow Equations and Frame Invariance

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In a number of previous notes, e.g. (1), we argued that the form of special relativity follows from the Lagrange equations $dL/dv=p$ and $E=pv-L$ assuming that $p=E(v)v$. Alternatively, it may be obtained from $dAction = 0 = -dE/dv t + dp/dv x$ where $x/t=v$ together with $p=E(v)v$. Here the Action is $-Et+px$ which is equivalent to the relativistic action $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$). We also argued that $A=-Et+px$ follows from the flow/flux equations: dA/dx (partial) = p and dA/dt partial = $-E$.

In this note we do not assume the form $p=E(v)v$. Rather we argue that $A=-Et+px$ should be invariant under constant velocity transformations. From nonrelativistic physics it is known that kinetic energy and p change if v changes. We assume that rest mass m_0 is proportional to energy because $p=mv$ is like an energy flux. At first glance one might think that spacetime (x,t) would remain unchanged as seen from a moving frame. We argue to the contrary in the following manner. If $(x,t)=(0,t)$ for a localized particle in a rest frame, then from the moving frame the particle seems to move. A moving particle with constant velocity should have x',t' such that $x'/t'=v$. Thus space-time cannot be the same from the two frames. Furthermore $-Et+px$ is of the form of a dot product with a $(1,-1)$ type of metric. Using these two ideas one may obtain the form of special relativity and the result that $p=E(v)v$. One may also obtain $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ((2)) ($c=1$).

It may be noted that c , the speed of light, does not enter the above discussions yet m_0 should be multiplied by a constant b such that b has velocity units if it is to be added to $.5mv$ in the nonrelativistic approximation. It may be noted from ((2)) that as $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ one has $E = pb$, but this is the equation of a classical wave. A particle with rest mass may travel through a vacuum so one needs a classical wave which does the same. This seems to point to light. Thus $b=c$ the speed of light.

Flux/Flow Equations

In previous notes we have argued that two flux flow equations seem to link special relativity to free particle quantum mechanics, classical mechanics and wave motion.

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p \text{ ((1a)) and } d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E \text{ ((1a))}$$

A simple solution is $A = -Et+px$ ((3)) which may be shown to be equivalent to the relativistic classical action $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$). What is important in ((1a)) and ((1b)) is that one thinks in terms of d/dx partial and d/dt partial which is already a quantum mechanical approach and that there is a minus sign in front of E which is linked to the metric of special relativity.

If ((3)) is considered to be valid (it matches the relativistic action) then it should hold in various frames i.e. a free particle may be viewed by a person in a frame moving with a velocity v . If one considers m_0 to be proportional to rest energy then one may have a localized particle at rest i.e. $(0, m_0)$ and $(x,t) = (0,t)$. Any t value is fine because a clock is ticking while the particle is at $x=0$.

From the point of view of a person in a moving frame, the particle should be moving with velocity v even at the initial instant. A particle at $x=0$ which then moves at velocity v should be at positions $x'/t'=v$. Thus spacetime (x,t) actually changes as viewed by a person in a moving frame. We argue that this must hold because there is an asymmetry at the initial instant. The particle is at rest in the rest frame, but moving from the point of view of the moving frame. Thus it must have special x', t' values i.e. $x'/t'=v$.

If $A = -Et + px$ is to be invariant under a constant velocity frame transformation, then $-Et + px$ is a dot product with an unusual matrix i.e. $(1, -1)$. One may use a unitary transformation to ensure the dot product remains invariant. This together with $v = x'/t'$ means:

$$\text{Transformation} = \begin{vmatrix} B & Bv \\ Bv & B \end{vmatrix} \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and} \quad t' = Bv + Bt \quad ((5)) \quad (\text{using } (0,t) \text{ as the initial point})$$

For ((5)) to hold: $B = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ which is the special relativistic result with $c=1$.

Applying this approach to $(0, m_0)$ yields:

$E = m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p = E(v)$ i.e. the generalized momentum result which is usually ascribed to a flux. In other words, the form of relativistic momentum follows from special relativity and then yields $m_0 v$ in the nonrelativistic limit. Furthermore, invariance of (p, E) yields:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((6))$$

Issue of c , The Speed of Light

In the above c , the speed of light, does not appear (other than the note that $c=1$). From nonrelativistic classical mechanics $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$. If this is to be added to m_0 to obtain a nonrelativistic limit of total energy then m_0 should be multiplied by b where b is a constant with the units of velocity. Furthermore p should be replaced with pb to have proper units in ((6)). The question is: What is b ? If one examines ((6)) in the limit $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ one has the classical wave result:

$$E = pb \quad ((7))$$

Thus b is the velocity of a classical wave which is a constant. A particle with rest mass moves through a vacuum so one seeks a classical wave which may also move through a vacuum. Such a wave is light and so:

$$b = c \quad ((8))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the solution $A = -Et + px$ of the flux/flow equations $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$ should hold in various frames moving at constant velocity i.e. one wishes

to have a frame invariant solution. For example, a particle at rest would seem to be moving when viewed by a person in a moving frame. It is clear from nonrelativistic mechanics that a particle with velocity has different momentum and energy than one at rest. We assume here that rest energy is proportional to rest mass so mov looks like an energy flux to zero order in v . What is not so clear is that space-time may change as seen from the moving frame. At first one might think space-time is a given framework that holds regardless of the moving frame. In this note we try to argue that the key point is that the frame is moving at a constant velocity. Thus for a particle at rest at $(x,t)=(0,t)$, it must be moving at this instant from the point of view of the moving frame. A moving particle (constant v), however, must take on x',t' values such that the ratio is v . Thus (x,t) cannot be the same as viewed from the two frames. (One may note that this argument does not consider light in any way so far.)

These ideas suggest that $-Et+px$ is a dot product with the metric $(1,-1)$ and that a transformation matrix is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} B & vB \\ vB & B \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{To have } 00 - tt = x'x' - t't' \quad B=1/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1)$$

Applying this matrix to $(0,m_0)$ yields: $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $p=E(v)/c$ ($c=1$). Thus the form of momentum follows from the special relativistic transformation. One also has $EE = pp + m_0m_0$. One may note that to have proper units one really has: m_0b and pb where b is a constant with units of velocity. If $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ then $EE = pbpb + m_0b m_0b$ becomes $E=pb$, the classical wave result. A particle with rest mass may move through a vacuum so one needs a classical wave which does the same i.e. light, thus $b=c$, the speed of light we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity from Lagrangian Formalism? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)